

TEACHING ENGINEERING PRACTICE IN CHEMICAL ENGINEERING VIA EXPERIENTIAL LEARNING

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Abstract

This paper argues that engineering practice should be the context of engineering education, and that engineering practice should be explicitly taught to students from the Diploma in Chemical Engineering (DCHE). It firstly summarizes key literature on the topic, as well as the requirements from the Institution of Chemical Engineers, UK; which accredits the program. It then outlines the DCHE's perspective on engineering practice which strives to balance both "traditional" notions of engineering practice, i.e. that of problem-solving; with a wider coverage that includes technical coordination in societal contexts. It argues that the actual learning experience for students in classroom study is significantly different from workplace learning; and that the present approach of relying on capstone projects does not adequately deliver the desired outcomes in terms of Singapore Polytechnic's graduate attributes. It goes on to propose that the teaching of engineering practice is best conducted by focusing on situated real world learning tasks, which will add a better context to learning. It shares a new initiative by DCHE based on the CDIO Framework that expose students to the practice of chemical engineering via experiential, contextual learning based on simulated real-world working environment. A pilot project of a learning task that involves role play (including faculty) that exposes students to time and resource constraint in completing a performance test run of a chemical reactor is described. It shares the evaluation results obtained from a group of over 50 DCHE Year 2 students. Key learning points and ideas for future work are also shared.

Keywords: *chemical engineering, engineering practice, CDIO, curriculum integration*

Introduction

The objective of engineering education is to prepare students who are deeply knowledgeable of the technical fundamentals and broadly prepared with the pre-professional skills of engineering (Crawley et al, 2007). However, it is often assumed in the literature that engineering design is at the heart of engineering education and is what distinguishes it from other

scientific areas within higher education (Williams & Figueiredo, 2010). Crawley et al (2008) suggested that engineering education should be set in the timeless aspects of the following professional context of engineering practice:

- A focus on the needs of customers
- Delivery of products and systems
- Incorporation of new inventions and technologies
- A focus on the solution, not disciplines
- Working with others
- Effective communication
- Working with resources

The CDIO (conceive, design, implement, operate) approach is a model of engineering education widely used by reputable universities around the world to re-design their engineering curriculum (Crawley et al, 2007). The Diploma in Chemical Engineering (DCHE) of Singapore Polytechnic (SP) had been using the CDIO approach to re-design its engineering education since 2007 (Cheah, 2013). This paper shares its effort in teaching professional chemical engineering practice in a core module entitled *Chemical Reaction Engineering*, currently taught to Year 2 students.

What is Engineering Practice?

The Institution of Chemical Engineers (ICHEME) UK, which accredits our course; stipulated "engineering practice" as one of the categories in its accreditation requirements. The ICHEME noted that the learning outcome for engineering practice as "Understand the ways in which chemical engineering knowledge can be applied in practice, for example in: operations and management; projects; providing services or consultancy; developing new technology" (ICHEME, 2012). This broad outcome is further elaborated as:

- Understanding of and ability to use relevant materials, equipment, tools, processes, or products
- Knowledge and understanding of workshop and laboratory practice
- Knowledge of contexts in which chemical engineering knowledge can be applied (e.g. operations and management, application and development of technology etc)

- Ability to use and apply information from technical literature
- Ability to use appropriate codes of practice and industry standards
- Understanding of the principles of managing chemical engineering processes
- Awareness of quality issues and their application to continuous improvement

Sheppard et al (2006) suggested that what is perceived as engineering practice depends on whose viewpoint is adopted – individuals and organizations engaged in engineering work, researchers who observed the work of engineers, and the engineering educators; and these viewpoints do not necessarily align with each other. Trevelyan (2009a) charged that very little is known about engineering practice due to lack of “systematically researched accounts”. He proceeds to suggest that engineering practice should include – after the initial “prediction” stage that incorporated customer needs into the designed solution – also the “delivery” stage which requires more time, resources, attention and effort (Trevelyan, 2009b). This approach is consistent with the broad descriptions of Crawley et al (2008). Our own take on engineering practice is a balanced coverage of problem-solving in the workplace which often requires the use of technical knowledge in an integrative manner; as well as that of technical coordination proposed by Trevelyan (2007), which is important at both “prediction” and “delivery” stages. We also see this as extending the learning outcomes not made explicit in IChemE's accreditation criteria.

Why Teach Engineering Practice?

There is a need to explicitly teach engineering practice if we want to achieve the intended learning outcomes espoused in our holistic education curriculum; which aims to deliver graduates who are life-ready, work-ready and world-ready. We need to ensure that learning is meaningful; as knowledge is context dependent and all learning takes place in a specific context. The contexts can significantly impact learning, so learning should occur in contexts to which it is relevant (Duffy and Cunningham, 1996). This is especially so in the case of engineering practice. Vincenti (1990) noted that “the inseparability of knowledge and its practical application is in fact a distinguishing characteristic of engineering”. Similarly, the study by Martin et al (2005) noted the complex interactions between communication, team-work and interpersonal skills in the workplace; and non-technical skills area are built on a technical basis, and therefore that a lack of confidence in the technical arena would hamper abilities in these other areas. The authors conclude that non-technical skills cannot be taught in isolation from the technical context in which they will be used.

Henning (1998) noted that the knowledge conveyed in the classroom tends to be situated in the context of the classroom and the school rather than the context in which the knowledge was created i.e. the workplace

where real-world engineering is practiced. When learning is removed from its context, the value of the knowledge and the relevance of that knowledge to the learner became depreciated (Lunce, 2006) and leads to what Henning (1998) called “cognitive dissonance” and reduced motivation in learning.

Most fundamentally, workplace engineering problems are substantively different from the kinds of problems that engineering students most often solve in the classroom; therefore, learning to solve classroom problems does not necessarily prepare engineering students to solve workplace problems (Jonassen et al, 2006). Workplace problems are ill-structured and complex because they possess conflicting goals, multiple solution methods, non-engineering success standards, non-engineering constraints, unanticipated problems, distributed knowledge, collaborative activity systems, the importance of experience, and multiple forms of problem representation. The authors noted that educators historically have assumed that learning to solve well-structured problems positively transfers to solving ill-structured, workplace problems. Much of the interest in engineering education today is on understanding and developing the skills of practice, as noted by Redish and Smith (2008): “What matters more is that the students learn the practice of science and engineering, not only the knowledge needed but how to use that knowledge in authentic contexts”.

Recent research has shown that learning to solve well-structured problems does not readily transfer to ill-structured problems. Patterson et al (2011) charged that “the importance of teaching engineering by reference to the surrounding conditions is perhaps so obvious that it should require no comment, except that the professors and professional engineers engaged in teaching have a tendency to forget that the formative and current conditions surrounding or experienced by their students are somewhat different from their own now and largely different from their own conditions when they were students.” Wulf (1998) went further to comment that “for the most part our faculty are superb ‘engineering scientists’, but they are not necessarily folks who know a lot about the practice of engineering.”

Current Approach in Teaching Engineering Practice

Educators often rely on final-year capstone projects serving as the platform for students to gain exposure to engineering practice. We argue that engineering practice should be introduced early in a student's academic life, so that they can better appreciate their chosen field of study; which we hope can lead to better motivation and hence, retention. Using capstone projects alone run the risk of different groups of students learning about engineering practice in unstructured manner, depending on the nature of the projects in question; some of which, for example, of pure research in nature, are not likely to provide much opportunity for learning about engineering practice.

In the case of chemical engineering, we also have another project, usually termed *Plant Design Project*,

where students are required to design a chemical plant using computer simulation software. We hold the position that such an academic exercise does not fit well with the notion of engineering practice as this is often the responsibility of professional engineering design firms: the typical “everyday engineer” hardly gets to model the entire design and operation of a chemical plant. Indeed, Domal and Trevelyan (2009) also noted from their study that design appeared to be much less prominent than expected. The rest of their study also resonates well with the author’s own prior industrial experience as a chemical engineer in managing one’s day-to-day work responsibilities.

More importantly, in our CDIO-type curriculum, we want students to be exposed early to the nature of work in the real-world setting, where one not only has to apply the necessary technical know-how, but also using various generic skills such teamwork, communication, good thinking, etc. We also learnt that many of our freshmen often enter their engineering training expecting their work to be “purely technical” (Vinck, 2004). We are motivated to rectify this long-held misconception about engineering education among our students.

Another approach that had been put forward to support engineering practice is what that of “situated learning” (or “situated cognition”) advocated by Brown, Collins and Duguid (1989). A critical aspect of the situated learning model is the notion of the apprentice observing the “community of practice” (Lave and Wenger, 1991). While the theories that underpin situated learning are relatively easily explained, implementing them in instructional settings can pose particular problems (Herrington and Oliver, 1995). These authors suggested the following critical characteristics in the design of learning environments to derive the benefits of situated learning in the classroom:

- Provide authentic context that reflect the way the knowledge will be used in real-life
- Provide authentic activities
- Provide access to expert performances and the modelling of processes
- Provide multiple roles and perspectives
- Support collaborative construction of knowledge
- Provide coaching and scaffolding at critical times
- Promote reflection to enable abstractions to be formed
- Promote articulation to enable tacit knowledge to be made explicit
- Provide for integrated assessment of learning within the tasks

Experiential, Contextual Learning for Teaching Engineering Practice

We find many similarities between the above with the requirements of CDIO Framework. Others serve to complement the pertinent CDIO Standards. Crawley et al (2008) refer to this as “contextual learning” in the CDIO approach; arguing that learning is more effective when teaching and learning experiences are set within

an environment or surroundings that help with understanding and interpretation. CDIO Standard 8 Active Learning is explicit in this regards, noting that learning “is considered *experiential* when students take on roles that simulate professional engineering practice, for example, design-build projects, simulations, and case studies.” This is supported by CDIO Standard 3 Integrated Curriculum and Standard 7 Integrated Learning Experiences. The former explained integrated curriculum as “a curriculum designed with mutually supporting disciplinary subjects, with an explicit plan to integrate personal, interpersonal, and product and system building skills”; while the latter refers to “pedagogical approaches that foster the learning of disciplinary knowledge simultaneously with personal, interpersonal, and product and system building skills. They incorporate professional engineering issues in contexts where they coexist with disciplinary issues.”

Materials and Methods or Pedagogy

Our work is based on an activity for the module *Chemical Reaction Engineering* entitled “Study of Temperature Effect on Reaction Rate using CSTR”. We have two main learning outcomes in the design of the learning task, which strives to achieve a balance in both the “traditional” and “emerging” views of engineering practice:

- (1) Traditional engineering viewpoint: to instill in students the mindset that solving a real-world problem often requires the integration of knowledge learnt or to be learnt in separate modules; or not taught in class at all
- (2) Emerging social and/or economic viewpoint: to expose students to a real-world scenario where; as a chemical engineer, he/she had to work with people of different department and background; some of whom may not readily identify with the engineer’s viewpoints as they are motivated by different social and/or economic concerns

The activity lasts for 3 hours in the laboratory and a written assessment is to be submitted in 2-week’s time. (Note: CSTR stands for Continuously Stirred Tank Reactor, one of the two main types of reactors used in the chemical industry). We designed a learning task that simulated workplace scenario whereby the students are assumed to have graduated and are working in a chemical company. The first part of the activity is to be completed in the laboratory using the set up shown schematically in Figure 1.

Students worked in groups of 3-4 members. In a nutshell, they are required to investigate the effect of temperature on the rate of chemical reaction. In order to complete the task, they need to conduct 3 experiments, subjected to time and resource (i.e. chemicals available) constraint. In addition, they were told that one or both of the feed flow meters may be faulty and they need to troubleshoot the process to ascertain the claim. The students are to assume different roles (supervisor, panelman, senior technician and/or technician). The

lecturer also role play as the Plant Manager. At the conclusion of the experiment, a debrief was conducted where students reflected on their learning experience.

Figure 1. Schematic set up for CSTR Experiment

This is followed by another role play where the lecturer now takes on the character of a Project Engineer from the Engineering Department while the students assumed various positions from other departments, i.e. as Maintenance Supervisor, Safety Officer, Financial Controller and Marketing Executive. In this part of the activity, the Project Engineer proposes a modification to address a safety concern in the plant which students will come to identify after they had worked on the plant. Each student is given a “game card” that reflect the position and viewpoint of the department he/she is representing. The lecturer then facilitates the discussion after each student presented his/her department’s issues and concerns over the proposal. Students are then asked to discuss the conflicting perspectives from the different departments.

At the end of the semester, we conducted a questionnaire survey where we asked students the following questions based on 5-point Likert scale: ranging from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 5 (Strongly Agree).

- Q1. “It is important that learning chemical engineering must take place in the context of chemical engineering practice, i.e. learning by performing tasks that a typical chemical engineer does in the real-world”.
- Q2. “This activity has helped me understand that real-world chemical engineering practice involve various skills and knowledge, often used simultaneously”.
- Q3. “The role play in this activity is useful in deepening my understanding of appreciating different perspectives from various parties involved in a typical project”.
- Q4. “This activity had allowed me to integrate knowledge from other core modules besides Chemical Reaction Engineering”.
- Q5. “This activity has increased my confidence in performing my future role as a chemical engineer”.

In addition, students are asked to elaborate on their answer to Q1, as well answer the following open-ended question:

- Q6. “Besides technical knowledge (i.e. effect of temperature on rate of reaction), explain at least four other key learning points, knowledge or skills you gained from this activity”.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 shows the responses obtained from the more than 50 students (N) who took part in the activity.

Table 1. Responses to Questionnaire Survey

Q	N	1	2	3	4	5
		Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
1	54	0	0	2	23	29
2	53	0	0	3	38	12
3	54	0	0	3	38	13
4	54	1	2	15	35	1
5	52	0	0	19	29	4

It can be seen from Table 1 that in general the activity, including the role play, was successful in creating the appreciation of the practice of chemical engineering. This is supported by answers given when asked to elaborate on their answers to Q1. Many wrote in their responses that they are able to relate to real-world chemical engineering through the activity. Many cited the need to know what they will be doing in the workplace as important knowledge besides the theories learnt in classrooms. More specific answers can be found in their responses to Q6. Besides teamwork and communication, time and resource management, which featured prominently among the replies, it is also clear that students understood the need to study an issue from multiple perspectives, as noted by some samples below:

“Empathy: Thinking in others’ shoes”

“I have learned to understand the different perspectives from different people”

“Dealing with differences in opinions and conflicts because of the role play”

“Every decision made does not just affect one department within a company”

“It is important to put ourselves in the shoes of others so that we can better understand one another’s concerns”

From these responses we can conclude that objective (2) has largely met the intention of learning task designed. The same, however, cannot be said of objective (1). The one item that did not feature too strongly from the responses received is the use of knowledge from different chemical engineering disciplines to solve process-related problem such as troubleshooting faulty flow meter and risk of high temperature excursion in the reactor. As can be seen from Table 1, there are indeed 3 responses that either “Disagree” or “Strong Disagree” to the statement in Q4.

In fact, a significant number of students had chosen “Neutral” for this question. This is mirrored by their response to Q5, where approximately the same number of students still did not feel confident in performing their future role as chemical engineers.

One of the challenges we faced, which is not unique to this activity, is the need for students to possess the necessary prior knowledge about chemical reaction engineering. For students carrying out the activity at the early part of the semester, such prerequisite knowledge is not yet taught to the class. The same can be said of other chemical engineering subjects taught in other modules. Knowledge, including conceptual knowledge, is central to the practice of engineering (Sheppard et al, 2006). More significantly, at the time of the activity (Semester 1), the students had not learnt the concepts of risk assessment, which is a central topic in a separate core module *Plant Safety and Loss Prevention*, which is only covered in Semester 2. We overcome this challenge by providing students with a one-page information sheet on risk assessment and its components (namely probability and consequence). Despite this effort, the need to use knowledge not yet taught; coupled with a “leant and forget” approach to studying, may be a strong contributing factor to the low score in the students’ responses for not being able to integrate what they had learnt in earlier modules.

Moving Ahead

Overall, we had used the adaptation of situated learning whose constituents can be represented schematically as in Figure 2 (from Herrington and Oliver, 1995). It shows that effective and meaningful learning is as much a part of learner participation as lecturer intention. From the figure, we can identify areas of improvement in all three circles. In terms of learning task, we believe there is a need to increase the adoption of such a learning approach into more activities in our diploma program. We had come a long way since our CDIO implementation (since 2007), and had integrated many skills into our curriculum, which besides the “ubiquitous” teamwork and communication, also includes creative and critical thinking skills, ethics, sustainable development, etc; the task scenarios in these activities are rather “straight forward” in the sense of specific skills to be covered. Often, consideration of other issues e.g. ethics, is an “add-on” to the problem at hand, in the form of separate questions during debrief or report assessment. The existing activities, especially those in Year 3, need to be reviewed to include more engineering practices so as to better reflect the complexities of real-world environment (authentic context) as encountered by chemical engineers. Work in this area has in fact been started by the first author and presented elsewhere (Cheah and Koh, 2013).

To effectively implement the revised activities, we will also need to design more integrated assessments. This is one area where faculty training will be beneficial in order to move forward. We will need to review and perhaps replace our existing pilot plants which had been

designed to serve specific needs of each core module, with more integrated plants. These measures, supported by the planned sequential course structure will help to better achieve the desired learning outcomes: that our students are able to utilise their knowledge in an integrated manner taking into account social and economical considerations.

Figure 2. Elements of Effective, Meaningful Learning

Lastly, to better support student learning, we felt that more scaffolding (a concept originally introduced by Vygotsky in the 1930s) need to be infused into the learning process; as well as getting students to engage in reflective practice (Schon, 1983) after they performed a key task. Lunce (2006) had reported that in the absence of reflection and debriefing, students tend to interact with a simulation (such as role play) as merely a game. Likewise, scaffolding is necessary to facilitate students building on prior knowledge, internalize new information, and to synthesize plausible solutions drawing from different subject matters.

Conclusions

This paper has presented our work in explicitly teaching engineering practice via experiential learning in the laboratory. While preliminary results showed that students appreciate the subject matter more and overall enjoyed the sessions despite increased workload and added stress during the role play, there remain much to be done to improve the whole learning process.

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